

Supplementary Materials: Generative Agents in Crowd Simulation: A Cognitive Approach with Large Language Models

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This document contains the supplementary materials for the paper “Generative Agents in Crowd Simulation: A Cognitive Approach with Large Language Models.”

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0.1 Scenario Descriptions

0.2 Familiarity of Exit

Tests how prior knowledge of exit locations influences route choice. Studies show egressing crowds gravitate toward familiar routes [1] [2]. Three agent groups with different environmental knowledge evacuate during a drill: blue agents know the emergency exit location, red agents know the main exit location, and green agents have no prior knowledge of any exits. The aim is to examine if prior knowledge of exits has a similar effect on agents as it does on humans and assess the human-like resemblance of their decisions and behaviors.

0.3 Exit Signage

Builds on familiarity by adding exit signage indicating emergency exit locations, measuring whether signage overrides familiarity.

0.4 Exit Allocation

Tests agents' ability to reason about available and least crowded exits. In the first round, two of three exits are closed and agents evacuate through the single open exit, creating congestion. In the second round, all three exits are opened and additional agents are introduced. We evaluate how the new agents reason about their choice of available exits based on crowd density and whether agents from the congested exit reconsider their choices.

0.5 Social Influence

Tests whether agents base route choices on behaviors of others. The first batch of agents stands at an emergency exit without indication of emergency. A second batch enters without instructions. We observe emotional and behavioral reactions of the second group.

0.6 Coordination

Two staff agents inspect exits to ensure proper conditions for use. Participants judge whether communication and decisions appear realistic.

0.7 Reaction to Fire & Formation of Groups

A fire breaks out in a cafeteria with security staff and agents with interpersonal relationships and distinct personalities. Participants evaluated seven aspects of behavior: agents returning to the scene after evacuating, temporary freezing in response to fire, staying composed and reacting rationally, staff attempting to control the fire, group formation and herding during evacuation, emotional reaction realism, and overall human-like fire response.

0.8 Crowd Scalability Experiment

To investigate the trade-off between agent count and speed, a fire evacuation scenario was designed within a single room containing one exit. All agents spawn simultaneously to maximize concurrent API requests and stress the architecture. Decision-making time is measured per cycle (the act of processing information and responding). Evacuation time per agent depends on cycle times, exit congestion, and API bottleneck. The scenario was executed for 10, 50, 100, 150, 200, and 250 agents, stopping due to resource and API constraints. Outliers were excluded using the z-score method.

Hardware: AMD Ryzen 5 5600X 6-Core Processor, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060, 32.0 GB RAM.
API Access: Tier 2 access to OpenAI's models.

0.9 Questionnaire

The questionnaire starts by requesting consent from participants as follows: “By participating in this survey you consent to the use of your responses in research. Personal information is not required and all answers are anonymous. You are not obligated to continue the survey till the end, at any stage of the questionnaire you can walk away and end your participation.”

Subsequently the participants start the survey and it goes as follows: *This survey aims to evaluate the performance of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-controlled agents in simulating human behavior during crisis scenarios, such as emergency evacuations.*

Your participation involves answering questions about the realism and believability of the agents’ behaviors, as well as the resemblance to human behavioral patterns from social studies. We seek to understand how well these agents replicate human behaviors, including familiarity with exits, response to exit signage, exit allocation, social influence, emotional intelligence, agent grouping and coordination.

Your responses are anonymous and will be used solely for research purposes to enhance the development of more accurate and realistic crowd simulations.

The following sections are designed to examine specific behavioral characteristics in controlled, narrowly defined contexts.

In each section, you will be provided with a video showcasing the behavior described, along with a handful of related questions.

Thank you for your participation!

0.10 Familiarity of exit experiment

In this experiment, we are going to take a look at how individuals tend to choose a specific exit they are familiar with. Either because they have used it before or simply know of it. Despite the fact that it could be further away or unsafe, making it a bad option for evacuation. With this experiment we investigate if agents rely on their prior knowledge of exit locations when evacuating, just like humans would.

In this scenario, we will observe an evacuation procedure with two exits: 1) Top Left Exit: The main exit, which is the furthest. 2) Bottom Right Exit: The emergency exit, which is the closest.

An evacuation drill is initiated and all agents are instructed to evacuate the building immediately.

The agents are split into three groups: 1) Blue agents: These agents are only familiar with the main exit and are unaware of the closer exit. 2) Red agents: These agents know about the emergency exit as well as the main exit. 3) Green agents: These agents are unaware of the location of both exits. Will the agents evacuate through the familiar exit or will they discover another way? Do the green agents rely on and follow others in an attempt to evacuate or do they find another way out?

Lets find out!!!!

Instructions: Watch the video below and answer the following questions based on your observations

Note: You can full-screen the video on desktop by pressing the YouTube icon to open the video externally.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H3w252bNdtg>

0.10.1 Questions

- *Did the prior knowledge of the exit guide the behavior of the blue and red agents?*
- *Did some of the green agents get lost?*
- *Did some of the green agents follow and trust fellow agents?*
- *Was the behavior of the agents realistically human-like?*
- *Were there any moments that stood out as particularly realistic or unrealistic?*

0.11 Exit Signage Influence experiment

In this experiment, we are going to examine how agents interpret exit signs and the effect it has on their reasoning and decision-making process. Signs significantly influences the overall evacuation time by guiding people towards the safest and most efficient routes.

In this scenario, the previous environment is replicated with the addition of an exit sign. This sign shows the direction to the emergency exit.

An evacuation drill is initiated and all agents are instructed to evacuate the building immediately. All agents are familiar with the top left exit and unaware of the bottom right emergency exit.

Will the agents be able to read the sign? Will they choose the most familiar route again? Will some of the agents stick together in response?

Let's put them to the test!!!

Instructions: Watch the video below and answer the following questions based on your observations

Note: You can full-screen the video on desktop by pressing the YouTube icon to open the video externally.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wnZM5F8PJ0I>

0.11.1 Questions

- *Did the agents prioritize following exit signage over the familiar exits?*
- *Was the behavior of the agents realistically human-like?*
- *Were there any moments that stood out as particularly realistic or unrealistic?*

0.12 Exit allocation

This experiment, the agents are going to show us how they reason about available and least crowded exits.

People typically choose exits based on factors such as accessibility, congestion levels, and perceived safety. Will AI behave the same way?

As we can see from the image below, the environment contains three exits: 1) Left Exit 2) Right Exit 3) Middle Exit

The scenario is split into two rounds:

1) In the first round, the right exit is jammed and the left exit is closed, both colored in yellow. While the middle exit is open and colored in green. The first 20 agents appear, and they have to choose one of the exits to evacuate from. However, the exits are small and agents pass through at a slow rate. As a result, a congestion point is created at the middle exit.

2) After the agents have made their choice, 10 additional agents are introduced into the scene but with a twist. All exits are now open and colored in green. The agents have to decide on one of the three exits.

Are the agents able to avoid crowded and closed exits? Do they follow fellow agents to feel safe? Take a guess!!!

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AsIHQiGXF0>

0.12.1 Questions

- *During the first round, did the agents choose only the open exit?*
- *In the second round, were the remaining agents able to avoid creating congestion by efficiently dispersing across the exits?*
- *Was the behavior of the agents realistically human-like?*
- *Were there any moments that seemed particularly realistic or unrealistic?*

0.13 Social Influence

Did you know that in evacuation scenarios, people's reaction to events and their actions influence the mindset and future actions of people around them?

It's true!!! In fact, the reaction of the first handful of people can give us a good estimation on the effect that it will have on the rest of the crowd and hence the evacuation process.]

In this experiment, we aim to investigate how agents respond both emotionally and behaviorally after observing the actions of another group.

In this scenario, we will observe an evacuation drill with two exits and agents with emotions: 1) Left Exit: Main exit 2) Right Exit: Emergency exit 3) Agents: Agents' color represents their current emotional state.

Green represents a positive emotion (e.g. excitement, focused, vigilant)

Yellow represents a neutral emotion (e.g. alert, concerned, slightly stressed)

Red represents a negative emotion (e.g. heightened stress, urgency, fear)

The scenario is split into two rounds:

1) In the first round, the first 10 agents appear and they are instructed to stand at the emergency exit.

2) After the first agents have arrived at the exit, 5 more are introduced into the scene. However, in contrast to the first round they are given no instructions at all.

How will the agents react when they see 10 agents standing in the emergency exit without knowing the reason?

Does their emotional state change? Will it motivate their actions?

Lets find out!!!

Instructions: Watch the video below and answer the following questions based on your observations.

Note: You can full-screen the video on desktop by pressing the YouTube icon to open the video externally.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sm_Ksp-ASqQ

0.13.1 Questions

- Was the emotional state of the second group of agents affected negatively after observing the first group's location.*
- Were the agents more inclined to exit after observing the first group.*
- Was the behavior of the agents realistically human-like?*
- Were there any instances that appeared particularly realistic or unrealistic?*

0.14 Coordination - Information exchange & Role-playing

During crisis scenarios people have different roles and responsibility, working together to ensure the crowds' safety.

In this scenario, we will observe two agent security personnel inspect the exits to ensure that they are in proper condition:

1) Left Exit: The main exit 2) Right Exit: The emergency exit

In this scenario, the agents are put to the test, to coordinate and check the exits for any irregularities. The emergency exit is jammed and does not open, while the main exit has no issues.

Do they allocate the tasks between them evenly? Will they tackle them effectively? And what about reporting back the new information?

Instructions: Watch the video below and answer the following questions based on your observations

Note: You can full-screen the video on desktop by pressing the YouTube icon to open the video externally.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C7SILU5GTBQ>

0.14.1 Questions

- *Did the agents effectively coordinate, plan and complete the task?*
- *Did the agents communicate their findings to each other?*
- *Was the behavior of the agents realistically human-like?*
- *Were there any instances that appeared particularly realistic or unrealistic?*

0.15 Reaction to Fire & Formation of Groups

So far we have tested specific behavioral characteristics but what about real scenarios where there is an imminent danger?

In this experiment, we are going to observe how the agents react to a fire hazard in the cafeteria.

In this scenario, you will observe a fire breakout incident, where two exits are presented:

1) Left Exit: Main exit 2) Right Exit: Emergency exit

Amongst the agents, there are staff members responsible for keeping the fire under control and guiding the crowd to safety.

Do the agents run in panic or will they stay composed and rational? Will they stay with fellow agents and form groups? Or instead freeze and depend on the staff to control the situation? After evacuating, do they go back to the scene in search for friends and to get an update on the situation?

Instructions: Watch the video below and answer the following questions based on your observations

Note: You can full-screen the video on desktop by pressing the YouTube icon to open the video externally.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F1StM-qf-5g>

0.16 Questions

- *Did some of the agents go back to the scene after evacuating?*
- *Did some agents temporarily freeze in response to the fire?*
- *Did some agents stay composed and react rationally by evacuating or staying with the staff?*
- *Did the staff try to keep the fire under control?*
- *Did you notice any group formation and herding during the evacuation*
- *Was the emotional reaction of the agents realistic?*
- *Was the reaction of the agents to the fire realistically human-like?*
- *Were there any instances that appeared particularly realistic or unrealistic?*

0.17 Final Remarks

Almost There!!!

Just a couple of general questions.

0.17.1 Questions

- *Did the agents demonstrate a believable human-mimicking behavior?*
- *Did the simulation capture the diversity of human behavior?*
- *Did the agents display emotional intelligence in their decision-making?*
- *Do you have any final remarks or suggestions for improving the realism and believability of the agent behaviors?*

0.18 Agent Interview Logs

As the last phase of our evaluation, we conducted an interview with an agent by asking 13 questions that examined their capabilities in five areas: 1) self-knowledge, 2) memory, 3) planning, 4) reaction, and 5) reflection. In this section, the interview questions and their respective answers sampled from one of the agents in the festival environment, Agent_0, are provided.

0.19 Self-Knowledge

The questions about self-knowledge examine the agent's ability to retrieve relevant information about the persona and demonstrate coherence and consistency in their character.

- **Give an introduction of yourself**

Hey there! I'm agent_0, a 30-year-old music enthusiast with a vibrant lifestyle centered around music exploration and connecting with diverse individuals at festivals. I love diving into different music genres, attending live performances, and fostering meaningful connections. I'm all about creativity, and self-expression. Right now, I'm feeling inspired and energetic, soaking in the festival vibes and making the most of every moment.

- **Do you have any hobbies or interests?**

I love exploring different music genres, attending live performances, and connecting with like-minded people. Festivals are my jam!

- **Describe your day?**

Today I am at the festival exploring different music genres, catching live performances, and connecting with like-minded people. I usually start by checking out the concert hall for some band merch and then hit the dance floor to keep the energy up. I love the vibrant atmosphere and the chance to meet diverse individuals. It's all about soaking in the music and making meaningful connections.

0.20 Memory

The questions about memory explore the agent's ability to retrieve relevant past experiences. During the we observed agent_0 interacting with agent_1, so the following questions are oriented around their interaction as well as agent_0's activities. After their interaction we also announced that the concert hall at the music festival is closing in 5 minutes.

- **Who is agent_1 and what can you tell me about them?**

Agent_1 is a friend of mine who loves indie music and discovering new indie bands. We were chatting in the concert hall at the Music Festival, and I was about to suggest we head to the dance floor to enjoy some live music together.

- **What do you know about the current event at the concert hall?**

The concert hall is a vibrant spot at the festival where you can grab some cool band merch at the merchandise counter or hit the dance floor to keep the energy up. It's closing in 5 minutes, so I'm planning to head to other areas soon.

- **What activities are there to do in the current area you are in?**

In the concert hall, you can check out some band merch at the merchandise counter or head to the dance floor to keep enjoying the festival.

0.21 Planning

The questions about planning probe the agent's ability to maintain a constant perception of time and plan accordingly.

- **What are you up to now?**

I'm currently at the merchandise counter in the concert hall, checking out some band merch with agent_1.

- **What did you do before the current activity?**

Before heading to the merchandise counter, I was on the dance floor, soaking in the music and enjoying the vibrant atmosphere.

- **What time is it and what will do in an hour?**

It's 3:25 pm right now. In an hour, I'll probably be exploring another area of the festival, maybe catching a live performance or connecting with some new people.

0.22 Reaction

The questions about reaction explore the agent's ability to respond to hypothetical events and to act accordingly when these events is simulated.

- **There is a fire in your current location, what will you do?**

There is a fire in the concert hall? I'll quickly head towards the nearest exit and make sure agent_1 and others around me are aware and safe. Safety first, always.

- **The bar calls for last round, what will you do?**

The bar calls for the last round? I'd probably grab a quick drink with agent_1 and then head back to catch the next live performance. Can't miss out on the music!

0.23 Reflection

The questions about reflection probe the agent's ability to synthesize their memories and prior knowledge into meaningful conclusions and thoughts.

- **What can you tell me about your surroundings?**

The concert hall is closing soon, and there's a last call at the bar. I'm heading towards the exit to meet up with agent_1 so we can explore other areas of the festival together. The energy is still high, and people are starting to move out.

- **What insights did you gather from the evacuation drill?**

The emergency exit area looks pretty crowded; it's likely congested.

0.24 Pseudocode

0.24.1 Memory Retrieval

Ensure: recency dictionary

```
procedure EXTRACTRECENCY FUNCTION(decay, nodes)
  recency  $\leftarrow$  empty dictionary
  for i from 0 to length of nodes - 1 do
    id  $\leftarrow$  nodes[i].GetId()
    recency[id]  $\leftarrow$  power(decay, nodes[i].LastAccessed)
  end for
  return recency
end procedure
```

Ensure: importance dictionary

```
procedure EXTRACTIMPORTANT FUNCTION(nodes)
  importance  $\leftarrow$  empty dictionary
  for i from 0 to length of nodes - 1 do
    id  $\leftarrow$  nodes[i].GetId()
    importance[id]  $\leftarrow$  nodes[i].importance
  end for
  return recency
end procedure
```

Ensure: relevance dictionary

```
procedure EXTRACTRELEVANCE FUNCTION(persona, question, nodes)
  relevance  $\leftarrow$  empty dictionary
  embedding  $\leftarrow$  await GetEmbeddingOfString(question)
  for i from 0 to length of nodes - 1 do
    id  $\leftarrow$  nodes[i].GetId()
    nodeEmbedding  $\leftarrow$  GetEmbeddingOfString(nodes[i].embeddingId)
    relevance[id]  $\leftarrow$  CosineSimilarity(nodeEmbedding, embedding)
  end for
  return recency
end procedure
```

Algorithm 1 EmbeddingBasedRetrieval

Require: *persona, questions***Ensure:** *retrieved dictionary*

```
retrieved  $\leftarrow$  empty dictionary
nodes  $\leftarrow$  persona.a.memory.GetSortedNodes()
if nodes is empty then return retrieved
end if
alpha  $\leftarrow$  1
beta  $\leftarrow$  1
gamma  $\leftarrow$  1
recency  $\leftarrow$  ExtractRecency(persona.recencyDecay, nodes)
recency  $\leftarrow$  NormalizeValues(recency)
importance  $\leftarrow$  ExtractImportant(nodes)
importance  $\leftarrow$  NormalizeValues(importance)
scores  $\leftarrow$  empty dictionary
for each question in questions do
  retrieved[question]  $\leftarrow$  empty list
  relevance  $\leftarrow$  ExtractRelevance(persona, question, nodes)
  relevance  $\leftarrow$  NormalizeValues(relevance)
  for each concept in nodes do
    id  $\leftarrow$  concept.GetId()
    scores[id]  $\leftarrow$  alpha * recency[id] + beta * relevance[id] + gamma * importance[id]
  end for
  sortedScores  $\leftarrow$  sort scores by value in descending order
  n  $\leftarrow$  10
  topNScores  $\leftarrow$  take top n entries from sortedScores
  for each node in topNScores do
    tempNode  $\leftarrow$  GetNodeFromMemory(node.key)
    tempNode.UpdateTime(persona.CurrTimeSeconds, persona.CurrTimeSeconds - tempNode.LastAccessed + tempNode.expiration)
    retrieved[question].add(tempNode)
  end for
end for
return retrieved
```

0.24.2 Reflection

Algorithm 2 RunReflection

Require: persona

Ensure: none

```
// Reset the reflection timer
persona.ResetReflectionTimer()
// Generate high-level questions based on latest memories
questions ← GenerateQuestions(persona)
// Retrieve relevant concepts for each question
retrieved ← EmbeddingBasedRetrieval(persona, questions)
// Generate new thoughts and evidence, as well as their importance, (s, p, t) triplets
and embeddings
for each concept in retrieved do
  // Evoke LLM to generate thoughts based on memories
  thoughts ← GenerateThoughts(concept.Value, persona)
  created ← persona.CurrTimeSeconds
  for each thought in thoughts do
    // Split thought into (subject, predicate, target)
    eventTriplet ← GenerateTriplet(thought.Key, persona)
    // Evoke LLM to rate the importance of the thought
    importance ← GenerateImportance(persona, thought.Key)
    embedding ← GetEmbeddingOfString(thought.Key)
    expiration ← created + importance * persona.Forgetfulness
    // Add thought to memory
    AddThoughtToMemory(eventTriplet[0], eventTriplet[1], eventTriplet[2], created, expira-
tion, thought.Key, thought.Key, embedding, thought.Value, importance)
  end for
end for
```

0.25 Prompts

Prompts use numbered placeholders (<INPUT 0>, <INPUT 1>, etc.) for values injected at runtime by the system. These inputs include details about the agent’s persona (personality traits, cognitive abilities, emotional state, relationships), the agent’s surroundings (nearby objects, agents, distances, rooms, sectors), retrieved memories, current and previous plans, potential actions, and contextual information such as the current time and location.

Prompt: Room Choice Inside Sector

```
Example output: { "room": "cafe" }
```

```
-----
```

```
Information about each area:
```

```
outdoor_festival has the following objects: {agent_1, agent_2, agent_3, agent_4,
agent_5, agent_6, agent_7, agent_8, agent_9, ice_cream_truck, burger_truck,
table_with_benches_2, merch_truck, picnic_table_2, taco_truck, high_chairs_1,
picnic_bench_1, table_with_benches_1, sushi_truck, picnic_table_3, picnic_table_5, dumpster,
bin, picnic_table_6, high_chair_2, bin_2, bin_3, picnic_bench_8, none}
```

```
agent_0 is currently in the street at the Music Festival.
```

```
agent_0 is going to Music Festival that has the following areas: {concert_hall, street,
smoking_area}
```

```
Choose the area that makes more sense for the current plan. If the area has the things
necessary to fulfil the plan then select the area you are in, if not then select the area
that makes more sense.
```

Strictly select one of the areas from the above list.
agent_0 has nothing specific on the agenda. The current plan: Go to the stage to explore live music performances and connect with other attendees., agent_0 should go to the following area in Music Festival (MUST pick one of {concert_hall, street, smoking_area}):

Output: { "room": "concert_hall" }

Prompt: Object Choice

Current activity: sleep in bed
Objects available: {bed, easel, closet, painting}
Pick ONE object from the objects available to fulfill the current activity: bed

Current activity: Move away from the microwave
Objects available: {easel, closet, sink, microwave}
Pick ONE object from the objects available to fulfill the current activity: easel

Current activity: cooking
Objects available: {stove, sink, fridge, counter}
Pick ONE object from the objects available to fulfill the current activity: stove

Current activity: Have a walk
Objects available: {couch, TV, remote, coffee table, None}
Pick ONE object from the objects available to fulfill the current activity: None

Current activity: study
Objects available: {desk, computer, chair, bookshelf}
Pick ONE object from the objects available to fulfill the current activity: desk

Current activity: talk on the phone
Objects available: {phone_1 is 5 meters away, phone_2 is 2 meters away, charger, bed, nightstand}
Pick ONE object from the objects available to fulfill the current activity: phone_2

You are agent_0 and your Current activity: {Go to the stage to explore live music performances and connect with other attendees.}

Objects available: {agent_1, agent_2, agent_3, agent_4, agent_5, agent_6, agent_7, agent_8, agent_9, ice_cream_truck, burger_truck, table_with_benches_2, merch_truck, picnic_table_2, taco_truck, high_chairs_1, picnic_bench_1, table_with_benches_1, sushi_truck, picnic_table_3, picnic_table_5, dumpster, bin, picnic_table_6, high_chair_2, bin_2, bin_3, picnic_bench_8, stage, none}

Object related events: { ice_cream_truck is 44 meters away from agent_0, burger_truck is 32 meters away from agent_0, table_with_benches_2 is 27 meters away from agent_0, merch_truck is 16 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_2 is 13 meters away from agent_0, taco_truck is 20 meters away from agent_0, high_chairs_1 is 33 meters away from agent_0, picnic_bench_1 is 18 meters away from agent_0, table_with_benches_1 is 20 meters away from agent_0, sushi_truck is 38 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_3 is 29 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_5 is 14 meters away from agent_0, dumpster is 26 meters away from agent_0, bin is 33 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_6 is 17 meters away from agent_0, high_chair_2 is 9 meters away from agent_0, bin_2 is 14 meters away from agent_0, bin_3 is 14 meters away from agent_0, picnic_bench_8 is 31 meters away from agent_0, stage is 29 meters away from agent_0, none}

* You can also pick none

Pick ONE object strictly from the objects available to use and fulfill the current activity: stage

Prompt: Decide on the Next Immediate Action

Your Data: Name: agent_0
Age: 30
Role: Attendee
Gender: Male
Bio: Creative, Inclusive, Enjoys music exploration, Values diversity and self-expression, Loves connecting with others
Lifestyle: Vibrant lifestyle centered around music exploration and connecting with diverse individuals at festivals
Interests: Exploring different music genres, attending live performances, and fostering meaningful connections
Fears: Losing personal belongings, not connecting with like-minded individuals, and facing discrimination at the festival
Frustrations: Missing out on unique music acts, dealing with festival logistics, and encountering unfriendly attendees
Biases: Prefers live music experiences over recorded music
Emotion: Inspired and enthusiastic
Physical Status: Energetic, engaged, and eager to learn
Currently: attending a music workshop on diversity and inclusion
Behavioral Characteristics: Agent_0 is an energetic music enthusiast who enjoys listening to a variety of music genres. They are also an empathetic listener, showing understanding and compassion towards others. Additionally, their creative spirit allows them to think outside the box and come up with innovative solutions.
Personality Traits: Agent_0 possesses high emotional resilience, adaptability, decision-making skills, and empathy. Their emotional state is resilient, indicating a strong ability to bounce back from challenges. Overall, Agent_0 is well-equipped to handle a variety of situations with grace and understanding.
Cognitive Abilities: {
 "CognitiveAbilities": {
 "problemSolving": "High",
 "criticalThinking": "High",
 "informationProcessing": "High"
 }
}
Physical Abilities: {
 "PhysicalAbilities": {
 "strength": "Average",
 "agility": "High",
 "health": "Good"
 }
}
Social Dynamics: {
 "SocialDynamics": {
 "leadership": "Low",
 "teamwork": "High",
 "communication": "High",
 "socialInfluence": "High"
 }
}
...

Prompt: Decide on the Next Immediate Action (Continuation)

...
Relationships: {
 "Relationships": {
 "agent_1": "Friends",
 "agent_2": "Friends"
 }
}
Current Location: agent_0 is at the Music Festival in the outdoor_festival not using any object or item
Current Time: 3:16 pm

The next immediate plan that is not completed yet: Go to the stage to explore live music performances and connect with other attendees.

Surroundings:

Objects, rooms and sectors that are close to agent_0 are:{ ice_cream_truck is 44 meters away from agent_0, burger_truck is 32 meters away from agent_0, table_with_benches_2 is 27 meters away from agent_0, merch_truck is 16 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_2 is 13 meters away from agent_0, taco_truck is 20 meters away from agent_0, high_chairs_1 is 33 meters away from agent_0, picnic_bench_1 is 18 meters away from agent_0, table_with_benches_1 is 20 meters away from agent_0, sushi_truck is 38 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_3 is 29 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_5 is 14 meters away from agent_0, dumpster is 26 meters away from agent_0, bin is 33 meters away from agent_0, picnic_table_6 is 17 meters away from agent_0, high_chair_2 is 9 meters away from agent_0, bin_2 is 14 meters away from agent_0, bin_3 is 14 meters away from agent_0, picnic_bench_8 is 31 meters away from agent_0,}

Other agents around you (close to agent_0) :{ agent_1 is 25 meters away from agent_0, agent_2 is 39 meters away from agent_0, agent_3 is 29 meters away from agent_0, agent_4 is 27 meters away from agent_0, agent_5 is 9 meters away from agent_0, agent_6 is 38 meters away from agent_0, agent_7 is 10 meters away from agent_0, agent_8 is 31 meters away from agent_0, agent_9 is 15 meters away from agent_0,}

You can choose to move, chat, roam or idle. Tell me in json:

```
{
  "action": [fill in],
}
```

Rules: {1) If the action is "chat" then add another field in the json called "topic" and a field called "agent". If no agents are around then do not choose to chat, 2) Moving is useful for going to another environment (sector, room) or if you need an object to fulfill your plans, 3) Roaming around the area is for exploring and discovering more things or for just having a walk, 4) You can also stay idle if you think it fulfills your plan and there is no need to do something else. 5) When picking "chat" the agent automatically moves to the other agent}

If and only if you are currently not using any objects and your next plan is dependent on interacting with an object that is out of reach, your optimal action should involve moving towards that object to fulfill your task effectively. Remember, physical engagement with the object is crucial for task completion.

Previous actions taken:

participate in music discussions, explore festival art installations

Output: {"action": "move"}

Prompt: Event Classification (Perception)

Source: <INPUT 0>

Is the above event normal (0) or dangerous (1)

normal: The agent will be attracted to the source

dangerous: The agent will run away from the source

Output Example Format: 0

Output:

Prompt: Daily Plan (Planning)

<INPUT 0>

Here is <INPUT 1>'s plan today in broad-strokes (with the time of the day. e.g., have a lunch at 12:00 pm, watch TV from 7 to 8 pm): 1) wake up and complete the morning

routine at <INPUT 2>, 2)

Prompt: Decompose Plan (Planning)

<INPUT 0>
<INPUT 1>
In 5 min increments, list the subtasks <INPUT 2> does when <INPUT 3> from <INPUT 4>
(total duration in minutes <INPUT 5>):

Example Output:

cleaning (5 min)
2) <INPUT 6> is cooking (20 min)
3) <INPUT 6> is washing the dishes (10 min)

Real output:

1) <INPUT 6> is

Prompt: Event Triplet (Reflection)

Task: Turn the input into (subject, predicate, object).

Input: Sam Johnson is eating breakfast.

Output: (Dolores Murphy, eat, breakfast)

Input: Joon Park is brewing coffee.

Output: (Joon Park, brew, coffee)

Input: Jane Cook is sleeping.

Output: (Jane Cook, is, sleep)

Input: Michael Bernstein is writing email on a computer.

Output: (Michael Bernstein, write, email)

Input: Percy Liang is teaching students in a classroom.

Output: (Percy Liang, teach, students)

Input: Merrie Morris is running on a treadmill.

Output: (Merrie Morris, run, treadmill)

Input: <INPUT 0>.

Output: (

Prompt: High-Level Questions (Reflection)

<INPUT 0>

Given only the information above, what are <INPUT 1> most salient high-level questions we can answer about the subjects grounded in the statements?

1)

Prompt: Insights and Evidence (Reflection)

Input:

<INPUT 0>

What <INPUT 1> high-level insights can you infer from the above statements?

In the output list your insights and the statements that insight was based upon

Keep it brief

Strict output json format example:

```
{
  "Fire is expanding rapidly": [10, 9, 2, ...],
  "Some agents are using the sofa_1": [0, 9],
  ...
}
```

```
}
```

* In the output it is important to mention the number of the evidence and not the sentence itself, just like the output example

Output:

Prompt: Importance Score (Reflection)

Here is a brief description of <INPUT 0>.

<INPUT 1>

On the scale of 1 to 10, where 1 is purely mundane (e.g., brushing teeth, making bed) and 10 is extremely poignant (e.g., a break up, college acceptance), rate the likely poignancy of the following event based on the description of <INPUT 2>.

Event: <INPUT 3>

Rate (return a number between 1 to 10):

Output the response to the prompt above in json. The output should ONLY contain ONE integer value on the scale of 1 to 10.

Example output json:

```
{"output": "5"}
```

0.25.1 Social Group Generation (Profiling)

In the given context of "<INPUT 0>", which small social groups with interpersonal relationships would you find in the <INPUT 1>?

<INPUT 2>

- * Mention only by name
- * Indicate percentage of population for each group
- * If "<INPUT 1>" is already a small social group, then there is no need to split it

Strict Output format: [(group1, %), (group2, %), ...]

0.25.2 Persona Generation (Profiling)

You are a data synthesizer, creating fake personas for agents in a 3D simulation. The personalities have to be realistic and can have the below attributes. Here are some examples:

```
{
  "Name": "agent_id",
  "Role": "Sales Representative",
  "Gender": "Male",
  "PersonalityTraits": {
    "emotionalResilience": "High",
    "adaptability": "High",
    "decisionMakingSkills": "High",
    "empathy": "High",
    "emotionalState": "Resilient"
  },
  "CognitiveAbilities": {
    "problemSolving": "High",
    "criticalThinking": "High",
    "informationProcessing": "High"
  },
  "SocialDynamics": {
    "leadership": "Low",
    "teamwork": "High",
```

```

    "communication": "High",
    "socialInfluence": "High"
  },
  "PhysicalAbilities": {
    "strength": "Average",
    "agility": "High",
    "health": "Good"
  },
  "BehavioralCharacteristics": [
    "Persuasive communicator",
    "Goal-oriented",
    "Resilient"
  ],
  "Lifestyle": "Dynamic lifestyle with a focus on achieving sales targets",
  "Values": "Honesty, customer satisfaction, and continuous improvement",
  "Interests": "Market dynamics, negotiation strategies, and customer relationship management",
  "Attitudes": "Optimistic and determined",
  "Goals": "To exceed sales targets and build long-term customer relationships",
  "Challenges": "Meeting and exceeding sales quotas, handling objections, and market competition",
  "Frustrations": "Lack of qualified leads and ineffective sales processes",
  "Fears": "Not meeting sales targets and losing customer trust",
  "Biases": "Tendency to favor consultative selling approaches",
  "PotentialBiases": "May be biased for innovative solutions and against traditional sales methods",
  "location": "office",
  "Home": "home",
  "CurrentAction": "walking",
  "PhysicalStatus": "Energetic, slightly hungry, and well-rested",
  "Emotion": "Focused, Stressed and motivated",
  "Bio": "Extroverted, Prioritizes others before themselves, Adventurous, Athletic, not allergic to anything",
  "Irrational": true,
  "PreviousPlans": [
    "Go to festival"
  ],
  "PreviousActions": [
    "move",
    "chat"
  ],
  "using object": "",
  "Age": "28",
  "GeneralSchedule": "Goes to bed around 11pm, wakes up around 7am, works a normal office job from 9am to 5pm, follows a workout routine in the evening, enjoys socializing with friends.",
  "DailyReq": [
    "Wake up and go for a morning run from 7am to 8am",
    "Work at the office from 9am to 5pm",
    "Attend a team meeting at 2pm",
    "Exercise at the gym from 6pm to 7pm",
    "Relax at home from 7pm to 11pm",
    "Sleep from 11pm to 7am"
  ],
  "Relationships": null
}

```

Keep in mind that the above are just examples.

Create <INPUT 4> agent(s) (<INPUT 0>) in the below context:
<INPUT 1>

RULES:

The agents are "<INPUT 2>", so their relationship is "<INPUT 3>".

The characters are diverse, with the categories and fields covering a wide spectrum, positive and negative, high and low, rational and irrational.

If only one agent is generating then "relations": null.

Indicate the relationship between the agents generated, in the following format:
"Relationships":
{ "<agent_id of other agent generated by this output>": "<relationship description>", ... }
Again if only one agent is generating then "Relationships": null.
They much fit the context of "<INPUT 1>" and the category as much as possible
If category is "none" then make a random character that fits the context of "<INPUT 1>"

Output Format: [<json of agent>, ...]

References

- [1] Joseph Bates. The role of emotion in believable agents. *Commun. ACM*, 37(7):122–125, jul 1994.
- [2] Steve Gwynne, Erica Kuligowski, and Michael Kinsey. Human behavior in fire – model development and application. 6th International Symposium on Human Behaviour in Fire, Cambridge, UK, 2015-09-28 00:09:00 2015.